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How does motherhood and fatherhood affect academic trajectories? A study on gender gaps in academic science in Uruguay¹

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Introduction

Despite improvements in the participation of women in academic science worldwide, there are still significant gender gaps in the entry, retention, and consolidation of scientific careers. Although the expression of these gaps has contextual particularities, it follows similar trends for both developed and developing countries (Caprile, 2012; López-Bassols et al., 2018). The evidence for Uruguay, although it is scarce, has shown similar trends to those observed worldwide (Tomassini & Robaina 2021; MIMCIT 2020; Gandelman and Bukstein 2016).

Explanations about what causes gender gaps are very diverse and range from forms of direct discrimination to explanations about unequal performance and skills for scientific activity. The influence of maternity and care burdens as an explanatory factor has been limited to the experience of some developed countries. Also, the vast majority of these studies are based on cross-sectional analyses, with only a smaller group using longitudinal data to study the effects of motherhood and academic careers throughout the life course (Fox & Gaughan, 2021, Cech & Blair-Loy, 2019, Mason & Goulden, 2004; Morrison et al., 2011; Wolfinger et al., 2009).

The main objective of this project is to study the effects of motherhood and fatherhood on the academic trajectories of researchers in Uruguay. The analysis focuses on three key dimensions of academic careers: 1) postgraduate training, 2) academic bibliographic publications, and 3).

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access to academic positions. This study is carried out from the construction of a novel database that combines longitudinal information on demographic variables and academic achievements. The project is based on an interdisciplinary approach that takes input from demography, economics, sociology, and Science, Technology and Society studies. The results are expected to contribute with empirical evidence, which can be used as a relevant input for the design of policies that promote gender equity in academic careers.

Data and Methods

To reach the objectives, it was necessary to build a database combining various sources of information. Our main source of information is the standardized Curriculum Vitae (CV) system in Uruguay, called CVUy, which includes variables related to training activities, access to positions, and publications, among others. Given the significant underreporting of the birth of children in the CVUy, it was necessary to conduct a survey directly asking researchers to provide this information. Additionally, the database is completed with administrative records from the public university (Universidad de la República - UDELAR) and the National System of Researchers (SNR). The conjunction of these sources allows us to have a novel database at the national level with updated information on academic trajectories. By combining all these sources, it was possible to build a novel national database with updated information on academic trajectories.

By defining researchers, meritocratic criteria are combined with positions and institutional affiliation criteria. The selected sample includes 76% of researchers nationwide, 2819 individuals, of which 55.6% are women. The methodological design uses descriptive, multivariate, and quasi-experimental techniques to explore the influence of motherhood and fatherhood on the three proposed levels of analysis: training, access to positions and publications.

At the same time, the project develops a systematic review of specialized literature. For this, data from 4269 papers from Web of Science and Scopus were processed, selecting 69 for review because they meet the requirement to study the link between motherhood and academic careers based on quantitative data. The PRISMA summary of this review is presented in Figure 1 in the Appendix.

Findings

The main descriptive results of the project for the three selected analysis dimensions are summarized below.

Table 1: Summary of descriptive results (average)

	Male	Female
Master's starting age	29.8	30
PhD's starting age	34.1	34.5
Master's length (years)	3	3.2
PhD's length (years)	4.8	5
Total of Published Papers	19.7	12.5
Total of Working Papers	2.1	1.6
Total of Books and Chapters	7.9	5.6

Source: Own elaboration based on CVUy, 2022

1) Postgraduate training:

Although the enrolment ages for master's and doctorate studies do not present significant differences by sex, women generally start later, and the gap is accentuated among those who had children. The average length of the training programs shows inequalities between men and women (Table 1), and even more between fathers and mothers. Preliminary results of the survival analysis -applying the Kaplan Meier method- show that there are significant differences by gender regarding the time required to complete doctoral studies. Women who had children before or during doctoral training are the ones with the longest calendar times (they graduate at older ages) and the longest durations (they take longer to graduate), both compared to men who have children and women who did not have children (Graph 1).

Graph 1: Cumulative proportion of doctoral degrees according to years of duration by sex and parental status

Source: Own elaboration based on CVUy, 2022

2) Academic bibliographic production

By using the data from CV it is possible to diversify the analysis of publications beyond that of articles, incorporating information on working papers and books, among others. The largest gaps by gender are found in the publication of peer-reviewed articles (Table 1), although there are significant differences by area of knowledge. To analyse these differences, it should be considered that the areas of knowledge have different behaviours regarding the types of dissemination format. The largest gap is found in the area of Health and Medical Sciences where, despite being a feminized area, the total number of articles published by women is considerably lower. The smallest gaps are observed in the area of Social Sciences and Humanities, where they are more accentuated in the case of publication of books and working papers. Similarly, the age of the authors and their positions are determining factors. While the differences observed in the articles published increase with the age of the researchers, the gender gap at younger ages is smaller, which may indicate an effect of cumulative disadvantages.

Part of these differences could be associated with motherhood, the burden of care and the interruption that women experience after the birth of a child. From analysing the evolution of the average number of publications per year, before and after the birth of the first child, it is observed that (Graph 2): (i). before birth, men and women show similar trends, as their age increases, the average number of publications per year increases, (ii). after the birth of the first

child, the trajectories begin to diverge, men continue to show an increasing trend in the average number of publications while women stagnate.

Graph 2: Number of articles published per year by sex and birth of the first child

Source: Own elaboration based on CVUy, 2022

3) Access to academic positions

Most researchers in Uruguay work at the public university. In our sample, 70% hold a position in that institution, most of them in the lowest levels (1 and 2) and men predominate in the highest levels (4 and 5). Similar findings were revealed after conducting the same analysis for mothers and fathers, although this population shows larger gaps at the highest levels. In turn, women reach higher positions at older ages.

Despite the differences observed by knowledge area, the expression of the gender gaps in the higher hierarchy position is maintained, as can be seen in Graph 3.

Graph 3: Distribution of researchers by position at UDELAR according to sex and areas

Source: Own elaboration based on CVUy, 2022

Similar trends are observed at the national level for the National Researchers System, where women are only 2 out of 10 researchers at the highest levels.

Systematic review

Preliminary results show that: (i) From the articles that study gender gaps in science, only a small proportion considers the role of motherhood and care responsibilities. (ii) A greater proportion uses qualitative data or descriptive statistics, and are not focused on estimating the effects or impact of motherhood on academic career dimensions. (iii) Those articles looking to approximate the impact or effects are more frequent towards the present, as of 2017, and the majority focuses on the North American or European academic system, no articles with this focus were found for Latin America and the Caribbean.

Final Remarks

The preliminary results show evidence that mothers and fathers show differences in their educational trajectories, and in access to academic positions and publications. The most critical points seem to be related to motherhood and the stage of culmination of the doctorate. Likewise, it is observed that the effects of motherhood could be affecting the average publications of women, which would generate cumulative disadvantages throughout their careers. Access to higher ranking and higher pay grades continues to show significant gaps for women who have and do not have children. Although there are differences by area, this glass ceiling remains one of the most rigid ones in academic science in Uruguay.

In the future, the descriptive results will become more complex by applying multivariate and quasi-experimental techniques, which will allow us to study these effects controlling for different attributes of academic careers and childbearing. In particular, controlling for the effect of disciplines, age, age of children, number of children, among others.

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Appendix

Figure 1: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews

Source: Own elaboration based on the COVIDENCE software.